

Research Article

Surface Response Methodology for Mild Steel Corrosion Control Using Udara Bark Extract as Inhibitor

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Abstract

This study employed factorial design (Random) experiments to generate surface responses of three factors – Extract Concentration, Time and Inhibition Efficiency. This is aimed at evaluating the effect of the independent variables (Concentration and Time) on the response variable (Inhibition Efficiency). The use of Udara Bark Extract as inhibitor in the control of acid corrosion of mild steel was examined during the study. In the bid to realize the research objectives, the design matrix for the two variables was varied at two levels (high and low) in accordance with the Yates Analogy. Experimental data generated were analyzed using the Design Expert Software, whereas Analysis of Variance and Regression Analysis were employed to assess the correlation efficiency of design factors. Surface plots of the interaction effects of the factors were also used to evaluate optimum conditions for the inhibition efficiency, and the correlation between the experimental process variables and the inhibition efficiency, which was evaluated using the central composite modeling technique. Inhibition Efficiency in 1M HCl medium was found to 30%, while that in 0.5M H₂SO₄ was 20%. The result of the ANOVA showed zero values for Coefficient Estimate and Sum of Square, indicating that the quadratic model suits the experimental data and the interaction of the factors were within acceptable level of significance. The even distribution of data points around the straight line in the plot of Experimental versus Predicted values demonstrates that there is good relationship between plot variables, and the underlying assumptions of the analysis were appropriate. The result, generally, suggests that the selected quadratic model was adequate in predicting the response variables for the experimental data.

Keywords: Surface Response, Mildsteel, Corrosion Control, Udara Bark

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Introduction

Failure of materials in service, generally, is traceable to miscalculations resulting from choice of wrong materials, improper treatment or fabrication of the material, improper design, wrong application of anodic or cathodic protection and wrong use or application of protective coatings (Amadi, 2006). In our industries today, corrosion ranks high in issues of great concern. It only takes one leak to render a length of pipeline inoperative. Occasionally, it could lead to a whole plant being shut down. In the deep, hot oil and gas oil wells, equipment is often subjected to aggressive corrosive conditions. High temperature and pressure conditions combine with constituents, such as hydrogen sulphide, chloride and salts, to form an environment in which many low alloyed and stainless steels perform unsatisfactorily. Mildsteel has been extensively used (under varying conditions), in chemical and allied industries, for handling alkaline, acid and salt solutions (including oil-derived compounds). And one way of protecting mildsteel from losing its integrity is the use of corrosion inhibitors. Offurum (2015) revealed that the known hazardous effects of most synthetic corrosion inhibitors are the motivation for the use of some natural products. According to the report, most of these natural products are non-toxic, biodegradable and readily available in plenty.

Design of Experiment (DOE) is the design of all information-gathering exercises, where variation is present, whether under the full or partial (fractional) control of the experiment. In testing, each experiment gets a minimum amount of measurable conversions, known as the sample size per data, for any statistical analysis (Amadi, 2006). Therefore, the more experiment you have, the more conversions you require. In an experiment, we deliberately change one or more process variables (or factors) in order to observe the effect such changes have on one or more response variables (dependent variables). The design of experiments is an efficient procedure for planning experiments so that the data obtained can be analyzed to yield valid and objective conclusions. Offurum (2011) reported that DOE begins with determining the Objectives of an experiment and selecting the process factors for the study. According to the report, an Experimental Design is the laying out of a detailed experimental plan in advance of performing the experiment. Well-chosen experimental designs minimize the amount of information that can be obtained for a given amount of experimental effort.

During any experimental design, all possible interactions may be included in the test (Full Factorial), or some of the interactions are selectively used (Fractional Factorial). For the vast majority of factorial experiments, each factor is assigned two levels-the high and low

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levels. But for computational purposes, the factors may be scaled (up or down) such that the high level is assigned a value of +1, and the low level is assigned a value of -1. In line with this arrangement, a full factorial design contains all possible combinations.

This research work is aimed at evaluating the effect of the independent variables (Concentration and Time) on the response variable (Inhibition Efficiency) in the control of acid corrosion of mildsteel, using Udara Bark extract.

Materials and Method

Sample Preparation

The aqueous extracts from the bark of the Udara tree (the Indian Apple, botanically known as *Chrysophyllum albidum*) that was used as inhibitor was obtained directly from the tree at Obinze in Owerri West L.G.A. of Imo State, Nigeria. It was thoroughly washed with clean water and sun-dried for 8 days. The dried (shredded) bark was ground into powder by means of electronic grinder, and was stored in a closed container, prior to use at room temperature.

Forty grams of the ground bark was added into 200ml of ethanol, contained in a 500ml round-bottom flask. The resulting solution was heated under reflux for 3hrs, allowed to cool to room temperature and then filtered, using a 'Whatman-14' filter paper. The filtrate obtained from the sample was measured, stored in air tight container and kept away from the sun.

Design of Experiment

In order to examine the combined effects of the different factors (Extract Inhibitive Concentration and Exposure Time) on Percentage Inhibition Efficiency, a central composite factorial design of 13 experimental runs was performed, using Udara Bark Extract as inhibitor. The design matrix for the two variables was varied at two levels (high and low), as indicated in Table 1. In order to avoid systematic error, the experiments were performed in accordance to the Yates Analogy, as documented in Box and Wilson (1951) and Offurum (2011).

Table 1: Basis for Design Experiment

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Name	+ alpha	High	Low	-alpha
Conc.(mg)	1165.69	1000	200	34.3146
Time(hr)	163.882	144	48	28.1177

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The generated experimental data were analyzed using the Design Expert software (trial version). Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Regression Analogy were employed to assess the correlation efficiency of design factors through the data generated. Response surface plots of the interaction effects of the factors were also used to evaluate optimum conditions for the inhibition efficiency. The linear, quadratic, and linear interactive effects of the process variables on the percentage inhibition efficiency were calculated and their respective significance evaluated by ANOVA test. The p-value was used as the yardstick for measuring the significance of the regression coefficients, where values of p that are less than 0.05 indicate that the coefficient is significant. The adequacy of the model was tested by the coefficient of determination (R^2) value as compared to the adjusted R^2 value. To develop a statistically significant regression model, the regression coefficients were evaluated based on the p-values. The terms with p-values that are more than 0.05 level are said to be insignificant, and thus are removed from the model.

The proposed model equation is given by:

$$Y_u = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_{12}X_1X_2 + b_{13}X_1X_3 + b_{23}X_2X_3$$

But the model, in terms of the actual values of the process parameters, resulted to the following equations for acid media under study:

Udara bark extract in 0.5M H_2SO_4 :

$$IE = 8.761 + 0.126A + 0.082B - 9.115AB - 5.547A^2 - 4.882B^2 \quad (1)$$

Udara bark extract in 1M HCl:

$$IE = 39.316 + 0.096A - 0.335B + 1.302AB - 4.766A^2 + 1.356B^2 \quad (2)$$

The experimental data were, also, analyzed to check the correlation between the experimental and predicted percentage inhibition efficiencies. The correlation between the experimental (process) variables and the inhibition efficiency was evaluated using the central composite modeling technique. A quadratic regression equation was fitted between the response variable (Inhibition Efficiency, Y) and the process variables (Extract

Concentration, X_1 and Time, X_2). X_1 and X_2 serve as the independent variables upon which Y depends. The interactive effects of the process variables on the percentage inhibition efficiency were studied by plotting three dimensional surface curves against the two independent variables, while keeping other variables at their base (zero) level.

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The 3-D/contour plots of the response (percentage inhibition efficiency), for the interactions between the variables, duly represent each of the media (H_2SO_4 and HCl) under study, for the inhibition on mild steel.

Results and Discussion

The results of the effect of Udara Bark extract on the milsteel in 1M HCl medium and 0.5M H_2SO_4 medium for predicted and actual (experimental) values are presented in Figures 1 and 2 respectively, while those of the interactive effect between concentration and time of the study sample on the mildsteel are presented for the two media considered (1M HCl and 0.5M H_2SO_4) are respectively presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Also, the analysis of Percentage Inhibition Efficiency and the Significant Effects of Udara Bark Extract (in 1M HCL) on Mild Steel, at varying degrees of freedom, is presented in Table 2, while that of the extract-in- H_2SO_4 (0.5M) is presented in Table 3.

Fig. 1: Predicted Values Versus Actual (Experimental) Values for Inhibition Extract on Mild Steel (1M HCL) of Udara Bark

Design-Expert® Software
IE

Color points by value of
IE:
77
24

Fig. 2: Predicted Values Versus Actual (Experimental) Values for Inhibition of Udara Bark on Mild Steel (0.5M H₂SO₄)

Design-Expert® Software
 Factor Coding: Actual
 IE (%)
 ● Design points below predicted value
 80
 30
 X1 = A: conc.
 X2 = B: time

Fig. 3: Effects of Extract Concentration and Time on Inhibition Efficiency of Udara Bark Extract on Mild Steel (1M HCl)

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Design-Expert® Software
 Factor Coding: Actual
 IE (%)
 ● Design points below predicted value
 77
 24
 X1 = A: conc.
 X2 = B: time

Fig. 4: Effects of Extract Concentration and Time on Inhibition Efficiency of Udara Bark on Mildsteel (0.5M H₂SO₄).

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Table 2: Analysis of Percentage Inhibition Efficiency and the Significant Effects of Udara Bark Extract (1M HCL) on Mild Steel

Source	Coefficient estimate	Degree of freedom	Sum of square	f-value	p-value (prop>f)
Model	2686.47	5	537.29	15.05	0.0013
A-conc.	2079.57	1	2079.57	58.27	0.0001
B-time	82.10	1	82.10	2.30	0.1731
AB	0.25	1	0.25	7.005E-003	0.9356
A ²	404.46	1	404.46	11.33	0.0120
B ²	67.93	1	67.93	1.90	0.2102
Residual	249.84	7	35.69		
Lack of Fit	249.84	3	83.28		
Pure Error	0.000	4	0.000		
Cor Total	2936.31	12			

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Table 3: Analysis of Percentage Inhibition Efficiency and the Significant Effects of Udara Bark Extract (0.5M H₂SO₄) on Mild Steel

Source	Coefficient estimate	Degree of freedom	Sum of square	f-value	p-value (prop>f)
Model	4013.37	5	802.67	24.61	0.0003
A-conc.	3374.17	1	3374.17	103.45	< 0.0001
B-time	79.02	1	79.02	2.42	0.1636
AB	12.25	1	12.25	0.38	0.5594
A ²	547.93	1	547.93	16.80	0.0046
B ²	8.80	1	8.80	0.27	0.6194
Residual	228.32	7	32.62		
Lack of Fit	228.32	3	76.11		
Pure Error	0.000	4	0.000		
Cor Total	4241.69	12			

Figures 1 and 2 indicate that the experimental data points were reasonably distributed near to the straight line, representing a good relationship between the experimental and

predicted values of the response; this implies that the underlying assumptions of the analysis were appropriate. The result also suggests that the selected quadratic model was adequate in predicting the response variables for the experimental data (Sinnott and Towler, 2009; Chauhan and Gupta, 2009). The results of the analysis of variance (Tables 2 and 3) show that the quadratic model suits the experimental data, as there are virtually no error in the Coefficient Estimate and Sum of Square (Amadi, 2006).

The analysis, also, shows that the interaction terms of concentration and time are within the acceptable level of significance, even though Inhibition Efficiency in HCl medium (30%) was higher than that in H₂SO₄ medium (20%) as presented in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. The interactive effects of extract concentration and time indicate that inhibition efficiency of mild steel increase in both corrosion media (H₂SO₄ and HCl) with increase in extract concentration (Oguzie, 2008). The analysis of variance indicated that the quadratic model was significant and adequate to represent the actual relationship between inhibition efficiency and the significant model variable as depicted by very small p-value (tending towards zero). This means that the model explains a good variation in the experimental data (Maiti, 2001; Perry et al, 1984). The high rate of correlation between the experimental values of the independent variables and predicted values confirms the adequacy of the model. The significance and adequacy of the established model were further elaborated by high value of the 99th coefficient of determination (R²) value; this

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is true because the adjusted R² value is in agreement with the corresponding predicted R² values (Amadi, 2006).

Generally, the high level of correlation between the predicted and experimental response proved that the regression model is adequate, explaining the variations in the experimental data (Treybal, 1981; Abdallah, 2004; Zucchi and Omar, 1985; Akalezi et al, 2012).

Conclusion

This study reassures, once again, the reliability of the use of plant extracts (such as the extract of Udara bark) in the control of acid corrosion of mildsteel. The process parameters investigated were all significant both at the linear and quadratic level, and the interaction effect of concentration and reaction time was statistically significant for the study sample, both in 0.5M H₂SO₄ and in 1M HCl for mildsteel. The high level of correlation between the predicted and experimental response proved that the regression model is adequate in explaining the variations in the experimental data.

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